

Decision-Making Practices and Teaching Effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Colleges of Education in Nigeria seem to face with challenges ranging from decline in teaching effectiveness, and low student outcomes. The study examined the relationship between decision-making practices and teaching effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Niger State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive research design of the correlational type. The population of the study comprised 920 lecturers in public Colleges of Education in Niger state. The sample for the study was 556 lecturers selected from two Colleges of Education in Niger state. Multistage sampling procedures, sample random technique and proportionate random sampling technique were used to select the sample for the study. Two set of instruments tagged "Decision-Making Practices Questionnaire (DMPQ) and Teaching Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ). The instruments were dully validated by experts. The reliability coefficients of 0.78 were obtained for the DMPQ and 0.85 for TEQ. The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of study revealed that the level of teaching effectiveness was high. Also, it was revealed that decision-making practices made significance contribution to teaching effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Niger State. Based on these findings, the study recommends that the Colleges of Education authorities should sustain the current high level of teachings' effectiveness through the use of appropriate managerial strategies such as participatory decision-making practices.

Keywords: Decision-Making Practices, Teaching Effectiveness, Colleges of Education

Introduction

Colleges of Education in Nigeria play a vital role in producing qualified teachers for primary and basic secondary education. The institutions regulated by National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), and are vital in the nation's teacher education system, providing the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) which qualifies graduates to teach in primary and junior secondary schools. In spite of this mandate, many of these colleges of education seem to face systematic challenges, such as resource inadequacy, managerial inefficiencies, to poor participatory governance structures which may directly and indirectly affect teaching and learning effectiveness. According to Ngini and Aguba (2024), colleges of education in Nigeria are structured in hierarchical order where decision-making authority is concentrated at the top management level (Provost, Deans, and Heads of Departments). However, the growing demand for academic quality assurance and teaching effectiveness necessitates a standard shift towards inclusive and participatory decision-making practices, where teachers as critical stakeholders are actively engaged in institutional decision-making that affects teaching delivery and student outcomes. Decision making refers to the process by which educational leaders select a course of action among alternatives to achieve desired outcomes.

In the context of colleges of education, this includes decisions about curriculum implementation, teaching methodologies, allocation of resources, staff development, and institutional policies. Decision making practices can be centralized or decentralized. Ngini and Aguba (2024), posits that teachers participate in decision concerning students and staff affairs but are often excluded from broader school planning. They recommend improved consultative structures to boost productivity. Also, Yusuf and Muslim (2023) reported that a moderate level teacher participation in decision making is a significant positive correlation between participation levels and teacher effectiveness.

Abdulrahman (2016) examined Employee Participation in Decision-making (PDM) and Firm Performance. The study employed Descriptive Survey Design; its data were collected through validated piloted questionnaire which was administered through mail to Three Hundred and Forty One (341) manufacturing firm. The result of the study revealed that there was a positive significant relationship that enhanced employee participation in decision making and firm performance.

Isichei and Godwin, (2015) conducted on a research on Decision making and the hospitality industry in Nigeria, a study of selected hotels in the federal capital territory in Abuja. The study adopted descriptive method and data were collected through primary means with the help of questionnaire. It used Multiple Regression method of analysis to generate result. The findings from the result showed that employee participation in decision making had great impact on the performance of hotels in Nigeria.

In another study by Chimaobi and Chikamnele (2020) on impacts of employee's participation in decision making on organizational performance using Government Owned Enterprises in Port-Harcourt, River State, as a case study, the population of study comprised managers and employees of the selected firm in Port-Harcourt River state. The sample for the study was given as 125. Out of the 125 copies of the questionnaire administered to the participant only 100 were returned while 25 were not returned. The study was analyzed using of tables and percentage while the three hypotheses were tested with the aid of ANOVA. The result from the research shows that employee participation in decision making has positive effects on organizational performance. This study was conducted in an organization on employee which is still in line with the present study but not directly about the academic staff in an educational institution like colleges of education which this study sets to address. Also, the researcher observed that most of these studies were majorly centered to determine the relationship between decision-making and employee (staff) performance while this study sets to fill the gap of job effectiveness of staff.

Teaching effectiveness in Nigerian teacher training institutions often suffers from systemic weaknesses: weak mentoring during teaching practice, poor linkage between theory and classroom practice, lack of feedback, and low pre-service teacher motivation. Effectiveness is a measure of job performance and desired quality. An employee's effectiveness is a measure of how much goals of the organization is being achieved through his commitment to and performance on the job (Eborunkan, 2019). The effectiveness might be high or low, depending on the input of the employee. Effectiveness can be determined through job evaluation and appraising the extent to which organization objective have been achieved.

Operationally, from the various review of literature on the concept of effectiveness, it could be inferred that effectiveness is the achievement of the purpose for which the various academic departments were established through effective staff membership. Making academic staff of the department effective in accordance with the laid down rules and regulations depends on the strategies of the Heads of Department.

Teaching effectiveness is one of the most important factors determining the quality of education in higher institutions of learning. The education system could be in terrible state if the academic staffs are not doing their job as expected. Therefore, effectiveness of lecturer is important for any educational improvement. Effectiveness of a lecturer refers to how he/she undertakes the professional duties assigned at a given time. These professional duties, according to Adepoju and Akinola (2017), include teaching, research and community services. Ahmad (2010) elaborated on the knowledge bases needed for effective teaching to include content knowledge, lesson planning, curriculum development, evaluating students' work, monitoring and supervising students, meeting with students and parents, classroom management, departmental and school meetings. All these centred on participatory decision making in curriculum of the school system.

Teaching staff are the greatest assets as well as major stakeholders in the higher institution (Osaat & Ekechukwu, 2017). Their main work is to teach and bring up the young generation of students to acquire skills and knowledge for growth and development. Teaching is a difficult task and demands serious commitment to be effective. Teaching involves adequate preparation of what to be taught through researches, regularity and punctuality to the class to implement what had been prepared. Teaching extends to evaluating the students through test, assignments and examinations, and particularly teaching extends to marking of examination scripts and production of results. Teaching effectiveness is achieved when a lecturer or a teachers attains desirable personal or organizational outcome. Therefore, measurement of the effectiveness of lecturers in Colleges of Education is based on teaching, research and community services and the attainment of these forms the bases of their effectiveness. However, for any tertiary institution to live up to the expectation of producing highly skilled labour and research output to meet the perceived economic needs, building new institution of civil society, encouraging and facilitating new cultural value and training socializing member of new

social elite, the teaching effectiveness of academic staff must be handled with special interest (Brennan, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

Effective teaching is generally known as important determinant of quality education delivery in colleges of education, which are fundamental in producing competent and professional teachers for Nigeria's educational system. However, in many colleges of education across Niger State, teaching effectiveness seem to remain sub-optimal, which can attest to by persistent challenges such as poor instructional delivery, low student engagement, inadequate curriculum implementation, and underwhelming learning outcomes. Among fundamental factors often ignored in addressing these challenges is the role of decision-making practices within institutional management structures. Decision-making practices in many colleges of education are frequently exemplified by centralized, limited staff involvement, and top-down administrative approaches, which may unintentionally suppress the creative and professional input of lecturers who are directly responsible for teaching-learning. When lecturers are excluded from key decisions concerning curriculum design, teaching methodologies, resource allocation, and pedagogical innovations, their commitment and teaching-learning effectiveness may be negatively affected (Ademiluyi and Aluko, 2023).

On the other hand, research has shown that participatory decision-making practices, where lecturers are actively involved in school governance and instructional planning, significantly enhance motivation, job satisfaction, and ultimately, teaching effectiveness. However, there is a paucity of empirical studies specifically examining how decision-making practices influence teaching effectiveness in the context of colleges of education in Niger State. This gap in knowledge presents a critical concern, especially in light of the national push for improved teacher education standards under the supervision of bodies like the National Commission for Colleges of Education. Therefore, it becomes imperative to investigate the extent to which existing decision-making practices within colleges of education in Niger State affect teaching effectiveness. Addressing this problem will provide valuable insights into how inclusive decision-making practices can be influenced to enhance instructional quality, promote lecturer commitment, and foster better learning outcomes in teacher training institutions. The main purpose of this is to examine the relationship between decision-making

practices and teaching effectiveness in colleges of education in Niger State Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to: Determine the level of teaching effectiveness in colleges of education in Niger State.

Research Questions

For the purpose of this study, one research question was formulated:

1. What is the level of teaching effectiveness in colleges of education in Niger State?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between decision-making practices and teaching effectiveness in colleges of education in Niger State.

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the correlational type was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 920 lecturers in the two public colleges of education in Niger State, out of which 556 lecturers were chosen using multistage procedures, simple random sampling technique and proportionate random sampling technique. The research instruments used for the study was questionnaire tagged “Decision-Making Practices Questionnaire (DMPQ) and “Teaching Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ). The instruments were duly validated by experts. The reliability coefficients of the instruments were 0.78 and 0.85 respectively. The method of data analysis was descriptive method such as mean, frequency counts and percentages. The research hypothesis was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 level of significant.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of teaching effectiveness in colleges of education in Niger State? In an attempt to answer this question, response to items in section B of the TEQ, were subjected to frequency count, percentage scores and mean scores. The total score on all variables were obtained together with the mean scores of each. The mean score was rated as low, moderate and high. Mean

Score that fell below 2.00 – 2.49 was rated as low, 2.50 – 2.99 was rated as moderate and mean score between 3.00 – 3.77 was rated as high. The result obtained is presented in table 1 below.

Table 1: level of teaching effectiveness in Colleges of Education

S/N	Job Effectiveness	Excellent		Very Good		Good		Fair		Poor		Total score	Mean Score	Decision
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	Teaching	205	36.90	232	41.76	74	13.32	24	4.31	21	3.71	2241	4.04	High
2	Research	96	17.31	149	26.85	265	47.73	33	5.88	12	2.23	1949	3.51	High
Total		301	54.21	381	68.61	339	61.05	57	10.19	33	5.94	4190	7.55	High
Average		150	27.10	190	34.30	169	30.53	28	5.10	16	2.97	2095	3.77	

Table 1 showed the level of teaching effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Niger State, Nigeria with regards to teaching and research. The result shows that 205 (36.90%) of the lecturers were rated Excellent on items that measured teaching, 232 (41.76%) were rated very good, 74 (13.32%) were rated good while 24 (4.31%) and 21 (3.71%) of the respondents were rated fair and poor respectively. In term of research, 96 (17.31%) of the respondents were rated excellent, 149(26.85%) were rated very good, 265 (47.73%) were rated good while 33 (5.88%) and 12 (2.23%) were rated fair and poor respectively.

The Table showed that teaching effectiveness was rated high in term of teaching with an average mean score of 4.04 representing 80.80 percent while in research, they were rated high with an average mean score of 3.51 which represents 70.20 percent. In all, the level of teaching’ effectiveness was rated high with an average mean score of 3.77 which represents 75.40 per cent. Hence, the level of teaching effectiveness was high during the period investigated.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between decision making practices and teaching effectiveness in Colleges of education in Niger State, Nigeria.

In testing this hypothesis, responses to items in Section A of DMPQ and items in Section B of the TEQ were subjected to statistical analysis, involving the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result obtained is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between decision making practices and teaching effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-value
Decision making practices	556	24.5000	3.0439	0.479	0.000
Teaching Effectiveness	556	90.4800	5.3150		

Table 2 showed r-cal. as 0.479. The result is significant ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) and the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was a significant relationship between decision making practices and teaching effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Niger State, Nigeria. The relationship between decision making practices and teaching effectiveness was average and positive.

Discussion of Findings

Finding from this study indicated that there was a significant relationship between decision-making practices and teaching effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Niger State Nigeria. This implies that teaching effectiveness in term of teaching and research is related to the degree to which they are involved in decision making practices, such as involvement in disciplinary policy matters, preparation of examination time table, decisions on development projects and recruitment of staff. This finding could be allowed to generate the notion that individuals tend to work harder at attaining a goal when they are involved in setting it. The finding could be premised on the fact that involvement of academic staff in decision making enhances communication among academic staff and managers. This finding corroborated the position of Udoh and Akpa (2017), which stated that where teachers were adequately involved in decision-making process, they would be committed and support the head of school to realize institutional goals just as opposition would be minimized. The finding equally corroborated the report of Chimaobi and Chikamnele (2020) that employees' participation in decision making had positive effect on organization performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from this study, it was concluded that lecturers in colleges of education in Niger State, perform their teaching and research duties in a manner that could facilitate institutional goal attainment. Also, participatory decision making and teaching effectiveness, it was concluded that, quality of teaching and research activities could be improved in the colleges of education by strengthening and institutionalizing some decision making that are found interconnected with teaching effectiveness.

Recommendations

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The colleges of education authorities should sustain the current high level of teaching' effectiveness through the use of appropriate managerial strategies such as participatory decision making.
2. It is recommended that managers should embrace the practice of assigning tasks to lecturers both individual and in groups in order to facilitate their effectiveness. This can be made effective by considering their capacity and experience in the task area.
3. Colleges of education authorities should ensure that lecturers attends seminars, workshops regularly and also further their studies when needed, this can influence the attainment of the institutional goal.

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